

MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING MODALITY: CHALLENGES AND INNOVATIONS OF MAPEH TEACHERS

Jaypee Sevilla Policarpio, MEd ¹, Fretzel Joy Sagal Candilado, MEd ²,

¹ MAPEH Department, Mabini Farm School, Cadiz City, Negros Occidental, Philippines

² MAPEH Department, Negros Occidental National Science High School, Victorias City, Negros Occidental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study aimed to identify the challenges and innovations by MAPEH teachers during the pandemic. This research utilized a phenomenological design in which the researcher explores real-life, in-depth information of 9 MAPEH teachers from DepEd. Validated structured questions were used as instruments in the study. The participant's responses underwent a thematic analysis using the Creswell method. Results revealed that the participants often experience emotional and mental stress caused by the pandemic's unanticipated changes, fear, and worry for their professions, lives, students, and families. They found adjusting to the current circumstances, where getting out, meeting new people, and traveling difficult. They are most likely to encounter workplace conflicts due to miscommunication and negligence of duty. Participants took steps to resolve these conflicts and create a harmonious workplace environment so that they could perform effectively as the teaching workforce of their respective stations. The teachers should only be the people administering the learning. They should be given time to help students and focus on being a teacher by giving the printing of module responsibilities to other possible qualified persons who should only focus on the said activity. The teachers should be given more emotional and mental health management programs or orientations to help them and their peers to correlate with the needs of their peers and promote social relationship developments to avoid conflicts and have a progressive performance as school faculty.

Keywords: *MAPEH teachers; Challenges; Innovations.*

INTRODUCTION

Learning is a key component of effective schooling. A person's ability to think and act is fundamentally and permanently altered by education. Nearly every element of life, including education, has been radically impacted since the COVID-19 Pandemic broke out over the world, and no nation has been exempted from these changes. Leaders from around the world have created extremely stringent regulations to break the link of COVID-19's expansion due to the difficulty in stopping the epidemic from expanding further. The World Health Organization (2019) proposed some requirements, including social and physical distance, which presented challenging implementation decisions for every nation. Similarly, the Philippine government ordered prompt, decisive, and appropriate action to reduce and remove the COVID-19 menace. DepEd introduced distance learning to prevent the spread of the infection and reduce affected population growth. During instruction, learning occurs between the teacher and learners who are geographically separated from one another using this method of learning delivery. This modality includes TV/Radio-Based Instruction, Online Distance Learning, and Modular Distance Learning. Teachers are required to report to the school for the manufacturing of modules, putting them at risk of contracting the COVID-19 virus. (Castroverde and Acala, 2021). Locally, the risk of teachers in Cadiz City has increased for the teachers who are assigned to their stations, who already faced hardships with natural calamities and endangerment from the presence of rebel groups before, now teachers are facing the risk of having the COVID-19 virus. This risk cannot be avoided especially when traveling long distances to their stations facing different people without knowing if they are already infected or not. According to Shah et al (2020), "Teachers are about average in terms of their risk of hospitalization with COVID-19 when compared to other working-age adults". It is in this context that the researcher aimed to gather more information about different types of challenges of the teachers; to dig deeper into how these teachers are at risk of acquiring the virus and endangering their lives to carry out students' learning; to acquire information of how teachers could be infected and could be the carrier of this virus risking not only their lives but also their families, neighborhood, and also with the people on their workplace; and to investigate what possible solutions that can be used and apply to this type of scenario. Most of the situations studied about Modular Distance Learning are common issues that apply to rural and urban schools. This study also focused on finding out how teachers manage to create innovations in this time of pandemic. This study explored the challenges and innovations made by teachers in the distance learning modality and developed findings that will help organizations to identify the problems and aid teachers who are assigned to different types of geographical locations and to help them create programs that will be helpful to their current situation facing different types of life endangerment as instruments of imparting knowledge, as an employee and as a person.

Review of Related Literature

This section presents the conceptual and related literature of this study in which the researcher reviewed in order to give her background of the study. Related concepts and studies that have significant bearings to the study are also presented. These concepts and studies are related to present investigation as to its study variables.

Challenges on Physical Health

There were 869 workers in all who participated in the survey. Weight gain was found to have the highest prevalence of physical health issues across all workers, with a rate of 40.97% (95% confidence interval = 37.69-44.24), and cabin fever had the highest prevalence of psychosocial issues, with a rate of 31.28% (95% confidence interval = 26.66-35.90%) among full-time working-from-home employees. Body weight changes, ergonomic issues, indoor environmental issues, and psychological issues were among the health consequences that were substantially (p for trends 0.05) correlated with the intensity of working from home. Eating patterns, sleeping patterns, and exercise routines were among the lifestyle modifications associated to the level of work intensity. Working from home can have a variety of negative effects on employees' wellbeing (Ekpanyaskul and Padungtod, 2021). The wellbeing of employees who work from home can be impacted in several ways. As a result, occupational health professionals need to be ready for pandemics in the future as well as risk prevention and health promotion in this "new normal" working life pattern.

The COVID-19 pandemic has put teachers in an unforeseen predicament where the lockdown has sped up the transition from conventional to online learning strategies and relationships have been affected by the avoidance of direct contact with others, with ramifications for their mental health. In this strange circumstance, physical activity appeared to be a factor that could prevent mental illnesses like depression or anxiety. The purpose of this study was to examine how the lockdown affected teachers' mental health and relationships in their three main spheres of lifework, family, and social interactions— as well as to determine what effect physical exercise played in each of the aforementioned factors. An online poll was created specifically with the aim of gathering both quantitative and qualitative data. The findings demonstrated that while the level of activity has little bearing on mental health, indoor physical activity prevents lockdown situations. Additionally, because of the increased workload brought on by the lockdown, teachers have reported higher levels of distress. In conclusion, it would be crucial to encourage teachers to engage in physical activity at home to prevent health issues among them in future situations. Additionally, for the teachers' successful professional development, training in blended or online instructional approaches would be essential (Aperribai et al., 2020).

The lockdown of children at home is another aspect affecting adults' personal, social, and professional lives because parents frequently take on multiple jobs and tasks at once (Orte et al., 2020). Teachers must manage online education at any level while taking care of other personal matters because educational administrations have not

stopped the academic year in the interim (Kebritchi et al., 2017). Additionally, it should be noted that Spanish teachers' working conditions were already difficult due to the high number of lessons (30–32 per week) and the teacher/student ratio of 25–36 (Vargas and Oros, 2021).

Additionally, all teachers should be ready to work with all learners or students in individualized and close connections in all teaching roles. As a result, they must play a significant part in their daily work and face-to-face interactions. When an online relationship must take the place of this direct touch, the work becomes considerably more challenging, and many other considerations must be taken into account. Since e-learning programs and activities are rarely taught in primary and secondary education curricula, teachers are generally not trained in them (Vargas and Oros, 2021). It should be stressed that instructors may play a unique and important role in times of crises. They can assist students with their psychosocial needs. Teachers can first foster an environment where students feel comfortable sharing their feelings and experiences, and then they can incorporate planned psychosocial activities into the teaching and learning process that can significantly benefit vulnerable kids.

The global health crises has resulted in a significant change in the way that teachers do their work (Sokal, 2020). These professionals were extensively researched prior to the pandemic, and findings indicated a significant level of work overload that resulted in work burnout. According to certain research, teachers may experience stress due to bad working circumstances, issues interacting with children and families, and organizational issues at work (Smetackova, 2019). Teachers in the educational sector must plan their workload and set aside extra time for caring for parents and guardians, making materials, and planning, the majority of which is done at home.

Additionally, teachers have reported experiencing a number of epidemic issues, including high prevalences of chronic non-transmissible diseases linked to a decline in quality of life (Lizana, 2020), high prevalences of obesity and low physical activity (linked to post-work fatigue and extremely late work hours), high prevalences of musculoskeletal disorders, burnout syndrome, depression, and anxiety. Due to the high proportion of women in this sector, these issues are also more severe in females (Avendao, 2020). Additionally, age is a significant factor that is connected to worsening mental and physical health (Fernandez, 2020). All of these occur in a setting of job overload exacerbated by teleworking and other variables that lead to a decline in physical and mental quality of life. The goal of this study was to examine teachers' health-related quality of life (QoL) before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Challenges on Emotional and Mental Health

Teachers' jobs are stressful even before the pandemic have become even tougher, with longer work hours, struggles to engage students remotely, repeated pivots from hybrid to remote to in-person instruction, not to mention fears that they or their loved ones could get COVID-19. Teachers' stress and anxiety have soared and their morale has plummeted during the pandemic, a flammable combination that could burn them out and lead them to leave their jobs. It is more important than ever, experts say, for districts to support their teachers by looking after their mental health. Even before the pandemic,

districts were paying more attention to teachers' mental and emotional wellness, offering sessions on mindfulness, yoga, exercise, and healthy eating. But COVID-19 has created wildfires of mental and emotional suffering across all job sectors, including teaching. The consulting group McKinsey & Co. surveyed 1,000 employers, and 90 percent reported that the pandemic was affecting the behavioural health of their employees. The Kaiser Family Foundation found that rates of anxiety and depression have quadrupled during COVID-19 (Gewertz, 2021).

All students' experiences in a classroom are influenced by the emotional climate. The teacher's emotional stability has an impact on that environment. All of the pupils who are affiliated with a teacher who has personal mental health issues may suffer as a result. There are numerous causes and underlying factors for mental health issues. Sometimes it is possible to spot certain signs and symptoms that are connected to emotional problems. It is crucial that strategies for aiding educators with emotional issues are found. Even if it's not always simple, doing this is essential for creating a positive teaching-learning atmosphere. When determining one's teaching style, self-analysis, teacher peers, school administration, and teacher preparation programs should all be considered. This is a task that cannot be completed by one person or organization. All educators need to be more conscious of the issue and willing to work toward improving the emotional wellbeing of all instructors, even though it is frequently believed to be a difficult topic to discuss (Miller et. al.,2018).

The pressure that online teaching methods have put on teachers is proof that this lockdown situation has caused serious problems in their lives, including long work hours, difficulties relating to the lack of physical touch, and challenges juggling personal and family responsibilities. We must undoubtedly draw some lessons from this experience. Given that parents have typically had to serve as a bridge to aid their children's teaching-learning process, it is crucial to research the level of digital competence that both instructors and students as well as parents possess (Cuetos et. al., 2020). Whether the health requirements demand a new lockdown or not, this is already a given.

On the other hand, because it can aid in extending borders and delivering education to every home, the COVID-19 pandemic situation has demonstrated both the benefits and dangers of online training. But as teachers' concerns have become apparent, there are numerous, primarily technical, obstacles that must be removed before this can be accomplished. These obstacles must be taken into account by universal digitization policies, by the authorities, and by public policies that prevent the digital divide. Teachers have highlighted that they may need training in the didactic and instructional value of each resource and method because there is not a direct correlation between what is done in the classroom and what has to be done online. Knowledge and skill-related restrictions could also exist. As shown by the findings of this study, in light of this challenging circumstance, it is also vital to develop better-structured teacher training plans that do not result in an excessive workload. Evidently, nobody was ready to switch from classroom to online instruction in a single day (Aperribai, 2020).

The pandemic has not only had an impact on pupils' mental health (CachónZagalaz et al., 2020), as teachers have also experienced significant stress since the crisis' inception. Recent research has shown that stress from having to quickly adjust

to conduct online classes during lockdown has affected teachers (Besser et al., 2020). As a result of the increased burden brought on by home teaching, this stress frequently comes with symptoms of worry, sadness, and sleep disturbance.

Although there were few studies done during the pandemic to measure the signs of stress, anxiety, and depression in teachers, the ones that were suggest that they had psychological symptoms, which emphasizes how crucial it is to reopen schools and institutions. According to a recent Arab study, this crisis has made instructors more susceptible to issues like anxiety, depression, marital violence, and divorce, which all limit their capacity to teach effectively. These issues are frequently associated with pandemic situations (Al Lily et al., 2020). An evaluation of the prevalence of anxiety among teachers conducted during the pandemic in three Chinese cities revealed a prevalence of 13.67%, with women reporting higher levels of worry than males and older instructors exhibiting more symptomatology (Li et al., 2020). Another study done in March in China revealed that 9.1% of instructors had stress symptoms, and that it was crucial to provide them with psychological support (Zhou et. al., 2020). Teachers also mentioned workloads, psychological issues, and weariness in a research done in Spain at the start of the pandemic (Prado-Gascó et al., 2020).

Additionally, past research has shown that utilizing ICT while working from home can lead to emotions of stress, worry, weariness, and poor job satisfaction (Cuervo et al., 2018), yet in a pandemic these were the only resources available to instructors.

Challenges on Social Health

It had only been a few days since COVID-19 had been named and the novel coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan had become a major international issue when the Chinese government first reported it. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) declared COVID-19 to be a pandemic as a result of this worry. When the imported and localized transmission of COVID-19 in the Philippines was discovered, the authorities saw it as a threat to the country's security (Nicomedes et al., 2020). As a result, on March 16, 2020, the Philippine government enacted the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) to stop the spread of COVID-19. However, the ECQ was extended until April 30, 2020 due to the rise in COVID-19 cases in the Philippines. Due to extended social isolation that causes loneliness, anxiety, sadness, and can even result in post-traumatic stress disorder, this health issue has produced public health emergencies that affect Filipinos across the country (Leite et al., 2020 cited in American Psychological Society, 2020; WHO, 2020). The Philippines' way of life has altered, yet not just Filipinos have experienced this transformation; because COVID-19 is now a global issue, everyone's way of life has also changed (Pan, 2020).

The researchers opted to investigate the potential effects of the COVID-19 outbreak on the population, particularly on teachers and how they handle the quarantine period, in light of the rise in COVID-19 cases in the Philippines. The basic level institutions' academic year would have ended in late March 2020 according to the Department of Education (DEPED), however COVID-19 caused the classes to be cut

short in the middle of the month. The Department of Education launched the DEPED Commons Project to act as an online platform for virtual lessons that teachers and even students nationwide can use as an alternative in the event that the suspension of face-to-face instruction during the school year 2020–2021 is extended due to the pandemic, but this is still in its trial stage and is not required. Similar to the suspension of classes, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) also recommended the use of alternative modes and distance learning, but these recommendations have not yet been implemented because virtual learning is still relatively new to the Philippine educational system.

Policies were developed to ensure the stakeholders' continued commitment to instructional and preventive measures, with a focus on teachers and children. These measures include the provision of alternative educational delivery methods and quarantine requirements (Commission on Higher Education [CHED], 2020; Department of Education [DEPED], 2020). Since teachers have not been educated for emergency online teaching, this new normal may cause them anxiety. Additionally, social isolation, home confinement, and class suspension, especially in higher education, can make teachers anxious. As a result, the two researchers opted to concentrate on an online survey that asked instructors about their experiences, attitudes, and strategies for coping with the COVID-19 pandemic-related fear.

Health Risk of Teachers During Covid-19 Pandemic

When it comes to looking for news about COVID-19 cases, 84.9% of Filipino instructors do so daily, with only 15.1% not doing so. On the other side, only 4.6% of people do not care if the material they are reading is reliable or not, while 95.4% make sure the information regarding COVID-19 is from a reputable or reliable source. It is crucial to be watchful and cautious about what news and information to believe in light of the numerous rumors surrounding COVID-19 and its detrimental effects on humans. In order to plan and protect themselves and their loved ones, people should be realistic and only obtain information on COVID-19 from reliable sources. This is further supported by the (WHO, 2020) recommendation that they do so once or twice a day.

When asked what the most crucial preventive measures are to fight COVID-19, 44% of Filipino teachers said they would avoid crowded areas, 6.4% said they would wear face masks, 16.5% said they would wash their hands, 20.2% would practice good hygiene, 2.7% would take vitamins, 7.8% would exercise, 1.4% would stay at home, and 0.9% would follow government guidelines. In addition, the highest percentage of Filipino instructors (98.2%) who see social estrangement in relation to COVID-19 prevention measures. Adopting information-dissemination techniques and launching awareness campaigns concerning COVID-19 are required by DEPED's memorandum 019 for 2020 in order to address stakeholders' fear and anxiety as well as to avoid, control, and promote healthy lifestyle choices.

Similarly, Wilder-Smith and Freedman (2020) suggested that social isolation hinders the spread of the virus. Social isolation is essential for preventing the spread of COVID-19, despite the fact that it makes people feel depressed and anxious. According to the authors (Roy et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020), it's critical for individuals to be aware of the precautions they can take to prevent the spread of COVID-19, including maintaining personal hygiene, using hand sanitizer, washing their hands, and donning masks. This also entails drinking lots of water, isolating oneself, and engaging in social withdrawal (Roy et al., 2020).

Additionally, only 73.9% of Filipino instructors do not want to speak to some acquaintances without a mask, and 89% prefer to carry disinfecting alcohol with them when they go out. Furthermore, 89% consistently check themselves for early symptoms of COVID-19. Similarly, 57.8% of teachers do not look forward to spending time with their friends by going to the movies in malls, 61% do not look forward to visiting public places like parks, and 85.3% disinfect their belongings before entering their homes. Only 44% of Filipino instructors who are subject to quarantine feel otherwise, and 56% do not find being at home during quarantine to be boring. On the plus side, 93.1% of people say that spending time with their family while under quarantine was positive. 25.6% of Filipino teachers prefer watching television given their usual activity during the quarantine period. In addition, 23.8% of teachers say they prefer to cook rather than engage in other activities like exercising (11.9%), sleeping (8.7%), playing mobile games (5.9%), writing (4.1%), gardening (5.9%), cleaning the house (3.2%), using Facebook or the internet (3.6%), praying (1.4%), reading (2.3%), or working on DepEd forms for checking (0.9%). In light of the findings about the attitudes of the Filipino teachers during the quarantine, instructors feel good about spending time with their family. This is a good preference among Filipinos as they give importance to their families. It has been in a Filipino culture that problems can be overcome having a family around. Likewise, teachers must learn daily routines such as physical activities to reduce boredom and find ways to strengthen positive experiences to others. Keeping regular contact with loved ones through phone, social media, social networks, and creating new hobbies, and thinking positively can help alleviate anxiety amid the global crisis (WHO, 2020).

Because of the psychological stress or anxiety caused by COVID-19, 92.7% of Filipino teachers are hesitant to enter crowded areas, 91.3% are uneasy using public transportation, 89.9% are cautious when touching anything in public spaces, 79.3% are cautious when touching their faces without washing their hands, 81.7% are unsure about eating in a restaurant, 91.7% have changed their lifestyles as a result of the COVID-19, and 92.7% are worried that their students. The results of this survey indicate that despite the COVID-19 pandemic, Filipino teachers have an optimistic attitude on life. However, psychological tension or anxiety is evident in their daily lives. This is because the epidemic transformed their lifestyle, making it so they can no longer perform the activities they formerly could (Pan, 2020).

During the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ), 74.8% of the Filipino teachers said that they spent more time on social media, and 78.8% said that they found a new pastime. In addition, 53% of Filipino teachers believe that spending time with family is the greatest approach to deal with anxiety during the COVID-19 outbreak,

followed by seeking spiritual direction (30.2%), talking to friends and loved ones online (8.3%), and surprisingly, talking to oneself (1.8%). When asked if their life would return to normal after COVID-19, 81.7% responded in the affirmative. Due to COVID-19's concern, Filipino instructors avoid crowded areas, which is also reinforced by what are thought to be COVID-19 preventive actions including avoiding crowded areas and social withdrawal. This claim supports the findings of the study on the stress instructors experienced during the COVID-19 outbreak.

While in quarantine, Filipino teachers have found a new hobby to help them cope with their worry. The majority of them use social media to connect with friends, pupils, and colleagues as well as to follow COVID-19 news updates to stay informed in an emergency. Similarly, teachers spend more time online because they engage in virtual learning projects and professional online communities to interact with peers. Due to the country's suspension of all national and regional conferences and events relating to education, they also devised ways to find a purpose (CHED, 2020; DEPED, 2020).

Challenges Encountered by Teachers in the New Normal (Modular Distance Learning).

Students' lives are significantly shaped by their education. One of the key components in delivering high-quality learning is the teacher. Numerous changes occurred in the educational environment as a result of COVID-19's establishment in the Philippines. The Department of Education's implementation of the manner of instruction is one of these. Most education systems have been forced to adopt alternatives to face-to-face teaching and learning because of the current COVID-19 dilemma. Many educational institutions transferred their operations online so that instruction could continue even while schools were closed (OECD, 2020).

The transition of teaching and learning in schools to modular distance learning made it more difficult for school staff to provide a foundational, high-quality education. DepEd officials always seek out ways to address issues and provide teachers and school administrators with the skills they need to be more productive in the field of modular remote learning (Bagood, 2020). In accordance with the "Most Essential Learning Competencies," designated teaching employees and Education Program Supervisors created modules starting in May 2020 in all topics for all grade/year levels over four quarters (Bagood, 2020). These self-study modules are already regarded as learning packages that include a pre-test, a conversation, and a number of evaluation/assessment tasks.

Acala (2021) claims that teachers attempt to address these problems using a variety of strategies as the Department of Education implements the modular distance learning modality. According to the study's findings, the secondary school teachers in Tacloban City's Division have a variety of coping mechanisms for the varied difficulties they face. One way to make a teacher's everyday work easier is through time management. Teachers are able to balance responsibilities and maintain a schedule of activities (Castroverde & Acala). In order to manage their workload, they should use 14 Consortia Academia Publishing (A partner of Network of Professional Researchers and

Educators) to prioritize tasks. If a teacher learns how to use his or her time effectively, duties like planning lessons, printing modules, and verifying modules can be completed.

They are given out to all students according to the class timetable for modular learning. Indeed, public school teachers all around the Philippines have embraced this method of instruction. In the midst of the pandemic, teachers are essential to maintaining the quality of education being provided. In the study done by (Lapada et al. 2020), it was shown that teachers were very aware of the COVID-19 pandemic's existence and effects. Teachers continue to assist pupils by creating modules as their learning guides despite the COVID-19 pandemic's risks.

As a result, the teacher takes on a new role as a catalyst for the student's growth as a member of their society and community (Martineau et al., 2020). Malipot (2020), however, emphasized the need of teachers discussing their issues with modular distant learning. According to Bagood (2020), it is standard practice for the department to train teachers not only for professional growth but also to become prepared for unforeseen circumstances. As front-liners in the educational system, they have undergone various training and seminars to be better equipped in delivering better education amid the COVID-19 pandemic.

According to a study by Ambayon (2020), modular instruction is more effective than traditional teaching methods in the teaching-learning process since it allows pupils to progress at their own pace. The students are stimulated and their interest is piqued by the unfettered self-learning method that includes quick reinforcement and comments that are added to practice exercises. As a result, this type of learning modality strengthens the student-centered learning strategy.

However, the introduction of modular instruction brought about a number of difficulties for parents, students, and teachers. According to the study by Dangle and Sumaoang (2020), the primary issues were a lack of school money for the development and delivery of modules, students' difficulties with independent learning, and parents' ignorance of how to properly mentor their children academically. Therefore, it is clear that using modular distant learning involves challenges.

Acala (2021) claims that in addition to evaluating student performance, teachers must also provide feedback to students in order to let them know how well they are progressing through the various modules. However, the researchers discovered that the way learning and instruction are currently delivered created a conundrum for teachers regarding how to approach students about their performance. According to the study's participants, text messages and social media sites like Facebook Messenger are used to communicate with both teachers and parents. However, not all Tacloban City students have access to these devices, and not all of them have the money to buy a bunch. Additionally, there are pupils living in places with subpar internet access. Due of these, teachers find it challenging to provide feedback on the work of their students and to let pupils know how their learning is progressing.

Recreational Activities as Innovations

Recognizing that a company's ability to gain a sustained competitive edge and increase customer happiness is the primary purpose of innovation (Orra, 2020). Due to the sharp increase in global competitiveness and consumers' ongoing quest to get the most value possible from their purchases, innovation has recently gained major importance for academics and practitioners alike. Recreation, which means relaxing and pleasant activities that people do voluntarily in their free time, is a concept that provides the physical and psychological renewal of individuals. The study was conducted on a total of 497 students, 248 men participating in recreational sports activities and 249 men who did not participate in any recreational activities. For this purpose, "Leisure Constraints Scale", which was developed by Alexandris and Carroll (1997) and was conducted in the study of the validity and reliability for Turkish Society by Karaküçük and Gürbüz (2007) was used.

The COVID-19 pandemic and its management are placing significant new strains on people's well-being, particularly those with pre-existing mental health conditions. Physical activity has been shown to improve mental as well as physical health. Increasing activity levels should be prioritized as a treatment target, especially when the barriers to exercise are greater than ever. Promoting physical activity has not traditionally been the remit of psychologists. Yet psychological theory and therapeutic techniques can be readily applied to address physical inactivity. We present theoretical perspectives and therapy techniques relating to beliefs about physical activity, (Franks, 2020) motivation to be physically active, and the sense of reward achieved through being physically active. We outline strategies to initiate and maintain physical activity during the COVID-19 pandemic, thereby benefitting mental and physical health. COVID-19 is demanding rapid and substantial change across the whole health care system. Psychological therapists can respond creatively by addressing physical activity, a treatable clinical target which delivers both mental and physical health benefits. (Diamond, 2021)

Psychological barriers have long been recognized as crucial to preventing activity, particularly amongst people with mental health problems. During this pandemic, there are likely to be additional barriers to increasing activity at the very time it may be most beneficial in alleviating physical and psychological stresses. For example, anxiety about leaving the house, the closure of gym facilities, and less opportunity to exercise with others. Whilst increasing physical activity has not traditionally been within the remit of psychological therapists in mental health services, it has been recognized that this may be an important modifiable factor for the improvement of mental health through COVID-19 (Diamond & Willan, 2020) and should be a focus of future research and endeavour (Holmes *et al.*, 2020). In the shifting landscape of the COVID-19 crisis, new priorities for treatment are emerging for which psychologists already have applicable skills. We propose that psychological therapists should engage in this area, and consider including physical activity as a treatable clinical target. COVID-19 poses a threat to the mental well-being of those with and without preexisting mental health conditions. At a time in which physical activity is so much needed and yet so challenging to perform, every health

care worker has a role in encouraging it. Psychologists are uniquely placed to assist with this by applying their knowledge of psychological theory and therapeutic tools. These could be implemented directly to help their own clients or to share with other members of multi-disciplinary teams so that a wider group of clients can benefit. COVID-19 is demanding flexibility and creativity to adapt care across the whole health care service. Now is the time for psychologists to apply their relevant skills to a target that has the potential to deliver both mental and physical benefits when these are most needed (Diamond, 2021).

These related studies aid the study in stating why this type of challenges occurs in teaching profession and increased their effects to teachers' holistic health during the Covid-19 pandemic were more hardships occurred. As a result, teachers' levels of stress and burnout have been high throughout these unusual pandemic times, raising concerns about a potential increase in teacher turnover and future teacher shortages. (Zamaro, 2021)

Research Questions

This study explored the challenges encountered by the teachers assigned in rural, urban, and coastal areas and the innovations they made in addressing these challenges. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the different challenges encountered by MAPEH teachers?
2. What innovations are made to address the challenges encountered by teachers?

METHODOLOGY

The participants in this study are 9 teachers assigned to rural, coastal areas, and urban areas. The researchers gathered the participants' descriptive data on demographic characteristics, including sex, and age. This research study employed purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, which is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys. The researcher acquired responses from three teachers from each identified school type. This research study employed a Phenomenological Qualitative research design and conducted a structured interview with the participants using a guide questionnaire. The guided questionnaire contains open-ended questions on the challenges encountered by the teachers and the innovations made to address such challenges. The questionnaire is composed of two parts, part I contains open-ended questions that explore the challenges they encounter, and part II contains open-ended questions about the innovations made to address the aforementioned challenges. The open-ended questions obtained information on MAPEH teachers' challenges and innovation in the Distance Learning Modality and were validated by the three experts in the field of MAPEH using the criteria set forth by Good and Scates. The validators gave the instrument a cumulative validity index of 4.5 (good). The researchers formulated a set of questions that are suited to answer the research

queries and were validated by three experts in MAPEH using the criteria set forth by Good and Scates. The researcher chose 3 participants for each school type. The researcher secured letters for the teacher participants for each school where the interview was conducted. The researcher started in urban areas where participants are accessible, then to the coastal area, and lastly, the rural areas observing and considering the IATF protocols and travel restrictions. Proper PPEs were utilized by the researcher and the participants for safety purposes. The responses of the participants were transcribed, read, and analyzed individually to identify the common challenges they face and at the same time, their innovations for the said problems. The results were written down verbally and identified the similarities and most commonly used innovation for each challenge stated. The researchers used thematic analysis that not only involves methods for describing data but also involves interpretation in the processes of selecting codes and constructing themes. Thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data that entails searching across a data set to identify, analyze, and report repeated patterns (Braun & Clarke 2006). Thematic analysis is an appropriate method of analysis for seeking to understand experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). The data was analyzed using Creswell Thematic Analysis, which is a systematic process for coding data in which specific statements are analyzed and categorized into themes that represent the phenomenon of interest. This study explored the challenges encountered by the teachers this school year, 2021-2022. Also, this study covered the innovations made by these teachers in addressing the challenges they have encountered. This research study employed a phenomenological qualitative research design and conducted a structured interview with the participants using a guide questionnaire. The said guide questionnaire was validated by the three experts in the field of Physical Education using the criteria set forth by Good and Scates. The data collection was conducted to 9 MAPEH teachers. Specifically, the target participants are three teachers assigned in rural, three teachers in coastal area, and three teachers in urban area. The researcher gathered information from these three teachers of each area regarding the challenges they have encountered in the Distance Learning Modality in this New Normal. This study was only limited to the MAPEH teachers for this school year, 2021 - 2022.

RESULTS

Table 1. Themes

Ergonomic Health Hazard
Stresses Caused by Covid-19 Pandemic
Isolation and Outdoor Activities
Worrying About Daily Life and The Modular Distance Learning
Losing Interest in Usual Routines
Relationship with Family and Loved Ones
Workplace Performance
Innovations Made by Teachers

DISCUSSION

Challenges of MAPEH Teachers amidst Covid-19 Pandemic

1.1. Ergonomic Health Hazard

This type of lifestyle, one of sitting and being sedentary for periods of more than an hour or two at a time, has a detrimental impact on our health and wellbeing. Unfortunately, there are dangers of sitting for long periods. But luckily, there are some office exercises and other initiatives you can take to combat it (Dempsey et al., 2018) As the pandemic hit our country, most of the teachers are loaded with tasks and activities which involves computer and tasks that are done through sitting down and almost spends these activities their entire day.

“Sometimes, mag abot palang sa school, mga average is 5 to 6 hours. Kay syempre pag abot sa school ma print module kag mang sort so indi ka maka halin-halin kapin pa amon printer while ga print indi sya pwede mabayaan. -Participant B

(As I arrived at school, the average time I spent sitting down is 5 to 6 hours and that is for printing and sorting of modules that I can not even stand up because the printer was broken and that it feeds to many papers at a time, so I really have to keep an eye.) Due to limited resources of schools, broken printers are one of the reasons why teachers tend to keep their eyes on the printers to avoid errors, which causes the reason to not to stand up in the whole duration of printing process. Doing such activity makes their body feel inactive.

The participant tended to spend more time sitting down while they are at their workstations. Most of the time, the participants stated that the time they spent sitting down while working ranges from 3 hours up to 10 hours which involves doing paper works, printing, and sorting modules for Modular Distance Learning. They had only 1- or 2-hour break or when taking personal necessities to give their body a chance to stand up.

*“Most of the time, sobra guro mga 4 to 5 hours. Example bi mga aga, mga 3 hours tapos paniyaga bi pungko naman liwat. Late nako permi ga abot bi, ga print module mga hapon mag after lunch break. Kung dala sa balay mga 9 hours gid.”
-Participant E*

(I sat down from 4 to 5 hours. In the morning I worked 3 hours then after lunch I proceeded to work again. I came late to school often since the Modular Distance Learning started and print modules, then if I had also included the time I worked when I was at home it would be a total of 9 hours.) They experienced back pain and lumbar numbness as they worked in the same position for a very long period. Thus, participants were exposed to the dangers of sitting for a very long period. Research has linked sitting for long periods with several health concerns.

They included obesity and metabolic syndrome, a group of ailments marked by elevated blood pressure, excessive blood sugar, extra body fat around the waist, and dangerous cholesterol levels. The risk of dying from cardiovascular disease and cancer appears to be increased by excessive sitting overall and by sitting for extended periods (Carter et al., 2018).

When you sit, you use less energy than you do when you stand or move. (Dempsey et al., 2018) Most of the participants were traveling to school by motor vehicle transportation and bus with a minimum of the 30-minute ride up to 50 minutes. Some participants stated that they traveled to their stations at an average time of 4 hours which tended to affect their body while sitting down as they waited to arrive at their school's location. Some participants have more challenges with traveling to their schools because the terrain to their schools is rough, rocky road and muddy.

There are some who stated that they rent room spaces and there is a participant who travels very far distance every day because of their children who needs to be breast fed.

“Ako daw naga board malang ko sir no. Even before pandemic naga board nako daan, para sakon hapos man lang. kay amon boarding house daw likod man lang sang amon school. Sa byahe sir haling d sa amon nga balay, sa hours sir, mga more than 4hrs gd ang byahe sir.”-Participant D

(I was renting a room in a boarding house even before pandemic, because it was easier for me. My boarding house was just at the back of our school, and I resided 4 hours away from our school.) To lessen the burden of travelling that far to their stations, they choose to stay at their rented room spaces and just travel back to their homes only if needed.

“Mapuli ko sa balay gab.e na mga 6 or 7 tapos may baby pa, indi pa makapahuway kay I have to take care pa skon baby kay ga breastfeed pa man. Everyday pa naman ko gapuli.”-Participant F

(I came home late, for about 6 to 7 in the evening and then I could not take some rest immediately because I must take care of my breastfed baby, and I do that every day.) There was a participant who bore the challenge of travelling a long distance to take care of the needs of her family and most especially her baby. There are some participants who choose to walk from their home to school, depending on how heavy or how many things they carry to go to work.

“Walking distance chill-chill lang. Mabalhasan lang gamay. Nami man kung ato ko sa school kay maka walking pa which is good for my body.” – Participant I

(I sweat a little and I liked walking to school from home if I was only in Alimatoc which is good for my body.) The participants also were having troubles and taking extra precautions while traveling to avoid being infected with the Covid-19 virus.

Thus, travelling to school is one of the biggest risks the participants take, during this time of pandemic. According to (De Vos 2020), COVID-19 will cause individuals to travel less and favor using vehicles or active modes of transportation over public transportation. This will lessen traffic and have an impact on people's health. Because of the

government's orders to stop the spread of COVID-19 and the associated fear, there was a significant drop in mobility recorded globally (Warren and Skillman, 2020).

Exercise is a subset of physical activity that is intentional, repetitive, planned, and intended to improve or maintain one or more physical fitness-related characteristics. (Brand et al., 2020) Most of the participants were having a hard time doing physical exercises to their schedules since the Covid-19 virus hit our country.

“Wala ko ka exercise, pag sugod Covid nag habok gid ko. Didto gid naghinugot. Halin sa medium nag large na or XL. Waay tyempo mag exercise.”-Participant E

(During the pandemic, I did not have a chance to exercise, and it made me gain more weight. I can hardly fit in my clothes.) Based on the participants, they experience weight gain due to lack of time this pandemic, due to busy schedules and workplace responsibilities. During this pandemic, activity restrictions are evident, which leads to unavailability of sports activities.

“Wala sir, amo lang na ang sige ko tindog kag sige libot sa school kung din ko sugo.on kag kung diin ko pakadtoon.”-Participant F

(None, I did not work out, just standing while working and roam around the school.) Even the restrictions have lightened, still the participants tend to have lost interest in engaging such activities. Although the situation is tough to some other people, others find a way to still be able to exercise.

“Siguro, oo ma consider man na guro ang tiktok? Pwede nan a guro no? kay every morning nan ga tiktok ko, ga saot-saot a boarding house. Daw amo na guro ang masiling ko sir nga daw ka form of exercise ko. Ang libot2 ko pagid sa amon school sir, gina consider ko man as exercise na lang sa akon.”-Participant D

(I think I considered dancing with the social media application called Tiktok as an exercise. I do it every morning, I dance at our boarding house and served as my form of exercise. Also, I can say that roaming around the school is also one of the exercises I do to keep myself healthy.) The participants have found an online social media platform where you would still be able to dance or exercise.

Thus, participants are experiencing difficulty engaging with the activities they do before the pandemic to keep themselves healthy, but others found some other ways to be fit. The negative effects of physical inactivity are a global-scale problem and some shocking reports have discovered that 2 million people around the world lose their lives in the face of this life-threatening inactivity epidemic (Yeo, 2020).

1.2. Stresses Caused by Covid-19 Pandemic

The participants were experiencing different types of stress due to different reasons. Those caused them to have trouble sleeping and accomplishing a certain task.

They might seem happy at times but most of the time they feel distress which make them feel troubled. Most of the participants stated that this time of pandemic they feel both happy and sad at the same time. In addition to the physical impacts, COVID-19 can have serious effects on people's mental health. A wide range of psychological outcomes have been observed during the Virus outbreak, at individual, community, national, and international levels. At the individual level, people are more likely to experience fear of getting sick or dying, feeling helpless, and being stereotyped by others (Hagger et al., 2020).

“Indi man gid totally happy, indi gd man totally sad, ara lang sa chaktohan. Satisfied lang sa subong nga system nga wherein indi man gid hago kayo. Especially sa modular, amo lang na eh kapoy lang physically sap ag print sang module. Medyo tawhay amo n inga set-up amo lang na galing kay kasubo kay ang learning wala lang galing.” - Participant E

(I can say that I was not totally happy and totally sad. I was just satisfied with our system now as a teacher because I was not that stressed with this modality. The stressful part is about printing modules because it caused too much hassle and it was really tiring and I was sad because the learning of students in this modality is not at its best quality.) The participant were not satisfied with the said learning modality in terms of the learning that the learners acquire, which is not efficient and accurate.

It is also said that printing of modules is a great burden to the teachers, which correlates to the statements of other participants. They experience sleepless nights just to accomplish printing sets of modules to their school's number of learners, which will take a lot of time using regular printers that produces modules slower than machines intended for printing large number of modules.

“Siguro kung ako, anxious kay daw ano abi, galagas ko permi sa mga modules mag print kapin pagid sang nag face to face nag id, lalagson nagid kung ano naman akon eh print sa limited modular.”-Participant C

(I think I was anxious about printing modules especially when the limited face to face was conducted. I have so many things to catch up on and to catch up also with printing modules for every batch of students.) In this case, the experience of printing modules every week is a troubling part to teachers. Their personal lives also are great influence on their emotional stability.

“While working, 50/50 happy and satisfied 50 percent sad. Indi man gid sya sad. Daw ka some part anxious. Kay pag even wala nako sa school like kung may mga ulubrahon gina panumdom ko just like subong may paminsaron ka sa school then may pinsaron kapa sa graduate studies and then may mga household chores Kaman nga gina paminsar man. May mga responsibility kapa nga iban nga gina pinsar.” -Participant B

(While working, I was 50 percent happy and satisfied and 50 percent sad, because I was anxious because I have so many things to tend to. I must think about my job as a teacher and at the same time I have to think about my graduate studies, and I have many

household chores to do. I was anxious because I have many responsibilities to do.) Some experiences outside their workstations also can be a big factor to their emotional health, and the participants stated that there are chances that their teaching or office work efficiency for a day they experienced stress are greatly affected. The participants also stated that the increase of workloads of the teachers is also a great factor to affect them emotionally and mentally.

Thus, participants tend to experience unstable expression of emotions caused by these challenges they face during this pandemic. Emotional instability is a catch-all term sometimes used to refer to unpredictable reactions and extreme emotions. While it is natural for everyone to experience a range of emotions, the term is usually used when discussing people who have more difficulty regulating their emotions (Abdel-Fattah, 2020).

Teachers are striving to keep themselves mentally and emotionally healthy with the transition of educational set up since the pandemic arrived in our country.

“Ang anxiety gid grabe gid, kay syempre nag worry gd ko. Ga worry gid ko sir kung paano, kung ano naman ang strategies naman bala nga gamiton ko sir sang pang tudlo sang MAPEH. Kay pag ano plang pag start sang modular learning.” -
Participant C

(When the Modular Distance Learning modality was implemented, I experienced a lot of anxiety, and I could not stop worrying too much. I worried if how will I conduct the MAPEH in this set up. I wonder what strategies I will use to still give them the lessons that they supposed to learn.) This statement implies the struggle of conducting MAPEH class in modular set up and on how they will maintain the activeness of outputs that the subject requires the students so comply.

In the beginning of transition, most of the participants stated that they were anxious about how they will print so many modules for different sections and in different learning areas. MAPEH components are separated when it comes to printing of modules, which is stressful to teachers because the number of modules that will be given to students per section will be multiplied into four. Most of the participants' reason of being anxious is the printing of modules which gave them sleepless nights just to print the complete set of modules that the learners should be received every week of distribution.

Keeping yourself away from anxiety is a challenging part as a person, but the participants are trying hard to let their stress go. The participants stated that they take time to give themselves a chance to unwind using gadgets, movies and other things which they think will help them to relieve themselves from stress. They also seek the presence of their loved ones to bond with and forget the stressful part of their jobs temporarily.

“Wala man kay if ever nga mabatyagan ko nga daw ka bug-at na daw ka burden gina buy-an ko ang work cause mentality health is important gid yah.”-Participant
A

(I don't let myself to be too stressful. Every time I feel like my work gives me too much burden, I let go of my work because for me mental health is very important.) The participant stated that he let's go of his work if he feels like tired and stress to keep himself mentally healthy. He also added that he gives time for himself to breathe some fresh air or play online games with his phone to let go of the stress experienced while working.

Thus, participants experience anxiety caused by sudden changes of Covid-19. As lockdowns and restrictions ease in various locations, some people find it extremely challenging to reacclimate to "normal" life. As the pandemic recedes, some consider this phenomenon as the next emerging mental health crisis. (Lakhan et al., 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic had greatly affected the health of people around the world, physically and emotionally. The pandemic dealt a great fear to people around the world because of its mortality rate that's greatly increasing. They fear going out from their homes and traveling to other places because they might be infected with the COVID 19 virus.

"Yes, in our workplace when there are times when the other teachers were exposed to someone who was infected with the virus, I feel unsafe and worry about being infected which will not only affect me but also my family if they will be infected also."- Participant A

Teachers are the front-liners of delivering learning to students, which they meet so many people every day to distribute the modules. They are scared while doing their job because their family would be in great danger also. There are times that they panic especially when there is information their location already has the virus.

"Siguro sir sa mga fake news sir, abi namon tuod-tuod syempre nag panic gid kami, wala kami kabalo kung ano amon himoon. So sang naka receive kami news nga diri kuno sa area namon may ara covid 19, syempre nag worry kami, tanan-tanan gin himo namon para lang makalikaw, nag overthink gid kami sir para malikawan namon ang covid nga sakit, pero fake news tu sya sir."-Participant D

(I think it was when there are rumors and fake news spread all over the community where our school is located. We panicked and we were confused and did not know what to do, and we worried so much, and we did all of the things to avoid getting infected. We reached the point where we overthink and stressed ourselves out but luckily it was just a fake news.) Based on this statement, fake news and false statements are also dangerous, because it will add up fear to the people around the community which has been said that there was infiltrated by the virus. As teachers of the community, they will feel alarmed not only for the students but also to their health and their families' sake.

"Ano siguro, ang kami mismo, isa ka pamilya, mostly sa amon nga pamilya nag positive kami, amo tu daw pag puli namon halin sa quarantine daw na stereotype kami dayon sang community, nga daw gin bansagan kami kuno nga higko kay tungod amo na nagka covid kami, after sato okay naman lang daw wala naman lang namon gin mind.

Wala man sila choice kundi mabakal sa amon sang feeds." -Participant G

(There was a time when my family and I were infected with Covid-19 and was tested positive. When we got home from the quarantine facility, people in our community spread rumors about us saying that we're dirty people because we easily got infected.

Later, we didn't mind it at all and the people of the community also because they have no choice but to buy some products in our store.) There is one participant who has experienced being infected with the COVID-19 virus which gave them a very negative effect caused also by their community. The participant stated that they are being stereotyped by their community of living an unhealthy lifestyle.

Of course, this situation can cause a great emotional effect through the people experienced being in this type of situation. Not only they worry of their health but also, they are worried about how people treat them within their community. Majority of the participants also stated that they are worried of traveling from their homes to their stations because traveling will give them a very great chance to get infected. The participants are taking extra precautions while traveling to avoid getting infected.

Thus, participants tend to get stressed during this time of pandemic. Some common causes of stress during the coronavirus pandemic are uncertainty, lack of routine and reduced social support, says (Robillard et al., 2020).

1.3. Isolation and Outdoor Activities

Most of the activities during this time of pandemic were held online. Most of the teachers spent their time working with computers and attending online seminars which leads to isolation most of the time. Teachers tend to spend less time with their families, friends, and their loved ones during this time of pandemic to avoid contact especially when they come home from their stations. In addition to the stress that might arise with social isolation or being restricted to your home, there is also the stress of worrying about contracting COVID-19 and losing loved ones to the disease (Hwang et al., 2020).

“Siguro mag abot na ang gab-e, kay syempre ako man lang isa sa boarding house te wala ko mayo upod tapos ara balang may bug-at ko bala nga mga task nga gina hatag sa akon sir, daw dira ko bala naga paminsar bala nga daw wala may naga bulig sa akon. Nga need ko gid tabang pero ayawan ka lang kis-a pangayo bulig kay syempre ang iban is indi mo man gid ma sabad.” -Participant D

(When it was nighttime and I was alone at my boarding house and I felt lonely. Every time I was given heavy tasks I was really seeking for help, and it made me sad because I did not have somebody to help me. That I really need someone to help me, but I did not have a choice and I could not bother any of my co-teachers because they also have tasks to do.) Based on the statement of the participant, every day during the night he felt lonely, especially when he needs someone to help him with his work. The participant resides in a boarding house near their school. He is 4 hours away from his family, and he has no peers or co-teachers staying with him inside the boarding house. He must rent a place to stay because his home was far from their school, And the effect of this situation is feeling of isolation or loneliness.

Although most of the participants were bothered with this state of being alone, there were some participants also who were alright with being alone. Most of them responded that although they spend so many times with their work, they still find time spend with their families and friends. There are some who enjoyed working alone because that was already what they used to. Most of them were comfortable with working without anybody beside them.

“Mas prefer ko gani nga daw ako lang bala isa, wherein maka focus Kaman bala sa imo nga ubra. pero lain man gid nga may tawo ka nga upod, ako bi kay daw wala gid ko yah ginasub-an usually during mga amo na (orientation) may ara Kaman isa ka cellphone samtang ga seminar maka facebook. Na anad naman ko nga ako lang isa kay sang una ako man lang di isa ga board. Te anad naman lang nga solo mode.” –Participant E

(I prefer to be alone where I can focus more on my work, but of course having someone beside you also gives a good feeling. I don't really feel sad when I attend orientations online and spend too much time with computers working with paper works because I have phone to use to divert my attention for every time, I feel stressed, and go to social media. I'm not affected of being alone anymore because ever since I'm used to it. In boarding house I'm always on solo mode.) In this statement it also added that they can focus more on their work if they are alone and not being affected with the thought of being alone because he was used to it for a very long time now.

Thus, participants experienced isolation due to their own choice, and because of the unavailability of company from families or friends. In a 2018 national poll conducted by Cigna, nearly half of 20,000 U.S. adults reported that they sometimes or always feel lonely, signaling that loneliness levels had hit an all-time high. In addition, 40% of poll participants said they occasionally or often feel lonely and their relationships are meaningless. According to a meta-analysis that Brigham Young University professor of psychology and neuroscience (Güzel et al., 2020), co-authored, being socially isolated increases health risks just as much as smoking 15 cigarettes a day or having an alcohol use disorder. Additionally, she discovered that social isolation and loneliness are twice as detrimental to one's physical and mental health as obesity.

During the pandemic, restrictions raised, and the conduct of different activities are limited. As the number of infected decreases, restrictions lightened, and some activities are allowed to be conducted. It was important for a person to be involved in activities where they can unwind and enjoy lessening the burden of stress. The activities that the participants stated are recreational, and for skill development where they enjoy doing as a form of diversion from stressful environment. During the COVID-19 pandemic the need for physical distancing due to virus mitigation efforts has exacerbated the isolation of many older adults (Haut et al., 2020) and has exposed younger adults to a similar experience (Ebrahimi et al., 2021).

“Pag start sang modular daw wala gid guro, kaysyempre sige lang ta hatag module. Siguro during modular, that time nag spend ko time ma enhance akon skill sa photography kay I have a camera na since 2016, but still wala ko japon

nab al-an ang kung mga anon a da nga part sang camera, sang nag try ko join sa Cadiz Light Catchers so mas nab al-an ko pagid ang kung ano gid ang photography about sa camera kag mag handle. Siguro amo na sya ang activity gid nga daaw nagpalingaw gid sa akon until now.”-Participant B

(When Modular Distance Learning started, I spent time to enhance my skill in photography because I have camera since 2016, but I did not have a chance to explore the features of camera, and how to properly use it. I joined the Cadiz Light Catchers for me to learn more about photography and how to handle the camera properly. I think that is the activity that I really enjoyed during the pandemic and until now.) In this statement, the participant explored her desired skill to be acquired. She engaged in photography with the help of professional instructors on how to improve their skills which gave her a lot of enjoyment and lessen the stress caused by the modality transition. Until then, the participant stated that she continues to enhance her skill and made it as a hobby. It is important to still go out and explore your community while enjoying what you do. To help others and as well as giving yourself a feeling of fulfillment.

“Sang pag ano, ga hatag kami mga goods kag school supplies sa mga bata, daw outreach program bale, kami nga mga teachers nag amot2 tapos gina select lang namon ang mga bata wherein daw mga kapigado gid bala tapos daw ga reach out kami sa ila, provide kami mga school needs mga gamit para sa modular set up. Happy gid, kay makabulig kami sa mga bata, daw ka warm sa pamatyagan and yes makadula sya sang stress.”-Participant E

(When we conducted our Outreach Program where we gave goods and school supplies to unfortunate children, we teachers shared money to support the program and we are the one who chose the deserving children to be given some goods and supplies for the Modular Distance Learning set up. I was happy that we conducted that activity and helped many children and I felt warm and lessen the stress I have felt.) Just like this participant stated that he involved himself in outreach programs where they help children with their studies and provides school supplies which children can use for their lessons and outputs in Modular Distance Learning. The participant stated that he felt an enjoyment and fulfillment doing such activities which gave him a sense of happiness.

A lot of activities were stopped since the pandemic started. Most of them are contact sports, team sports and other activities which involved a large number of population to be conducted. Therefore, most of the participants chose recreational activities to keep themselves from being stressed. They focused on outdoor activities which has less contact with other people, like taking long rides, hiking, and eating. Some others enjoyed their work, while conduction Home Visitations and monitoring their students in their homes, and there is a participant who enjoys seminar on how to create modules which gave her a chance to be with some other teachers who has more experience than her.

“Siguro ang seminar namon ubra module, for farm school syempre bag.o palang ko sa Deped, daw damo ko na meet nga teachers from other schools. Damo man ko na learn sa ila kay dugay na sila, ga share experience.”-Participant G

(I think when we had our seminar workshop for creating modules. I am a newly hired teacher at Deped and that activity was good for me because I met many teachers from other schools and I've learned a lot when they share different experiences.) Where she said that she feels happy hearing all the experiences shared by other teachers from other schools.

Thus, participants were troubled but were able to find time and things to enjoy. As a result, a unique situation arose, in which most of the world's population was confined to their homes, with only medical staff and other essential workers being allowed to leave their homes on a regular basis. Several studies of previous quarantine episodes have shown that psychological stress reactions may emerge from the experience of physical and social isolation (Brooks et al., 2020), but participants tend to still find ways to distress. According to recent research from the American Psychological Association, feeling stressed may cause you to go to great lengths to satisfy a craving for a drink or some sweets, but you're not likely to enjoy the indulgence any more than someone who is not stressed and consumes the same treat just for pleasure (Turna et al., 2021).

1.4. Worrying About Daily Life And The Modular Distance Learning

Participants stated that they sometimes feel like worrying about their job, the learning modality and about their personal lives as this transition began. Over the years, various authors have pointed out that education workers show a high risk of developing anxiety, stress and burnout as a consequence of being exposed to a wide range of work stressors in their daily activities (Salari et al., 2020).

“Panalagsa sang modular kay wala man gid sya paminsaron kayo kay sang first year of modular ta division mann ang nag provide sang modules. But then this school year siguro ang pinaka ano gid yah nga frequent daw every other day or every night nga may gina panumdom ka its because nga manumdom ka nga ma print ka and then san-o mo matapos print nga may inug sort ka pa nga manug release ka na sang module pero wala mo pa na tapos print. And then there are other pa nga mga school related nga mga reports nga dapat mo eh submit so this year siguro mostly every night nga amo sina.” -Participant C

(The very first time that the modular distance learning started, we have not felt any stress and worrying about our modules because it was provided by the division office, but then this school year, I think this is the most stressful one. I worry more frequently than before thinking if it was possible for me to print the required number of modules that will be distributed every week and there are times that I could not really finish printing all the modules. I also worry about other school reports that should be send immediately and it made me overthink almost every night or every other day.) The participants stated that as this transition began, the number of paper-works that should be done by the teachers increased.

It made them feel stressed because the schools receive the memorandum very late, and the reports should be done and submitted immediately.

Participants stated that the most stressful obligation during this Modular Distance Learning modality is the printing of modules, especially when the division offices do not provide modules to schools anymore, which leads to the situation where the teachers are the ones who should print the modules for their students. Most of the participants' concern why they worry so much other than printing of modules is the threat of Covid-19 pandemic where they panic and have trouble sleeping thinking that they travel every day to their school and meeting many people inside their stations.

The participants stated that during the pandemic they were in favor of the Work from Home scheme which made them feel safer working just inside their homes and avoiding close contacts to other people which could be a possible virus carrier.

According to a survey by the company Stannah, the COVID-19 pandemic had changed our living situations where the household expenses arise during the Covid-19 Pandemic to provide the needs of their family, 2 of the participants stated that they are unable to sleep soundly at night due to thinking about money and their loans (Celik et al., 2020).

“Every month, there are times that I often think about my loans. In work, I'm comfortable with my performance as a teacher, and the only thing that bothers me most of the time is money and loans.”-Participant F

According to one participant, she often sleeps late at night and has trouble sleeping, overthinking about loans and their money and it was also the problem of the other participants who stated.

“Bale, ano eh nang, sa money. Kis-a amo na mapinsaran mo nga wala kana kwarta. Ginapinsar mo nga daw malubong ka na sa utang.”-Participant B

(Money, I often worry and think that what should I do, because I don't have money anymore and I worry too much because I seem drowning with too many loans.) Thus, participants tend to worry more often facing these challenges during the pandemic. This stress has often been accompanied by symptoms of anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbance as a consequence of the increased workload resulting from home teaching. (Perez-Cano et al., 2020).

Stress is actually a normal part of life. At times, it serves a useful purpose. Stress can motivate you to get that promotion at work, or run the last mile of a marathon. But if you do not get a handle on your stress and it becomes long-term, it can seriously interfere with your job, family life, and health (Khademian et al., 2021). Stress has increased in the teaching field since the pandemic hit our country. Stressed that are acquired in work and personal life, which has a great impact to teachers' well-being and work performance. MAPEH teachers played a difficult job in printing modules, because MAPEH subject is 4 different areas that is handled by a single teacher.

“Teachers must print four modules just in one subject per week, Music, Arts, P.E. and Health. For me, printing of modules is the very stressful part in this modality for subjects and is multiplied by the number of students for every section, and every grade

levels. Other subjects will only just print 50 modules per section but us MAPEH teachers will print 200 modules just for one section.” -Participant C

The participant is troubled and stress every week about printing of modules compared to teachers in other subjects. This causes the participants to sleep very late in order to print the desired number of modules every night.

Printers were also one of the problems of teachers because regular printers are not designed to print large numbers of documents and prints slower than a carbon photocopier said the participants. To consider the learners in rural areas where the internet is inaccessible for online learning, the Modular Learning modality is currently used by all public schools in the Philippines. Modular learning is a form of distance learning that uses Self-Learning Modules (SLM) and is highly convenient for most typical Filipino students. It was also the most preferred learning system of most parents/guardians for their children. The SLM is based on the most essential learning competencies (MELCS) provided by the Department of Education. The study was conducted to determine the issues and concerns about the use of Modular Distance Learning Modality among teachers (Talimodao and Madrigal, 2021). The participants stated that in this said subject, giving remediation activities and as their subject teacher they will be the ones who must think of activities that is suited for the children and hit the desired competencies. Calculating grades is one of the challenges that were encountered by MAPEH teachers, because they will calculate four sets of grades just for one subject which is divided into four.

“Ayawan pagid ko hatag grado kay ako lang isa MAPEH sa amon school. Amo nag ani wala ko nagpangayo advisory kay ka kapoy.” -Participant E

(I'm having a hard time giving grades to my students because I'm the only MAPEH teacher in our school, and that's why I didn't bother to ask for an advisory class to lessen my burden.) The participant states that being a MAPEH teacher, giving grades to students is one of his stressful experiences and other than that, school reports are one of the obligations that made the participant feel more stressful.

Thus, the participants often experience stressful experiences in the transition of modality. It is a well-established fact that overwhelming stress and trauma take their toll on physical and emotional health (Turna et al., 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic is definitely a health issue. Schools are closed globally. The country and the entire world are facing new challenges brought about by an unforeseen public health crisis. There is no doubt that, like many other aspects of daily life, COVID19 has had a significant impact on students, teachers, and educational organizations around the world. (Robillard et al., 2020).

1.5. Losing Interest in Usual Routines

Nowadays, it was typical to lose interest in hobbies. As everyone is aware, the world was put under complete lockdown as soon as the virus struck. By that time, the most of us had already considered engaging in our hobbies, which had previously served as our escape from the always busy and stressful lives we had been leading but then we lost interest to these hobbies. Feelings play a significant role in psychological well-being of

students hence directly affecting all aspects of their academic lives (Kaur et al., 2020). Specifically, positive feelings (e.g. enjoyment and interest) were found to be associated with students' attention, concentration, engagement, and persistence in learning activities which positively correlate with academic achievements. We all know ever since the pandemic hit; the world went into a definite lockdown. By then, most of us had already thought of connecting with our hobbies, which were our solace from the daily hectic and stressful life but eventually stopped enjoying, leading us to lose interest in hobbies said by (Ameis et al., 2020) a Digital Marketing Enthusiast, Consultant, Investor. The participants tend to lose interest in their hobbies, like sports, games, or online games.

“Oo, may ara lets say for example sa sports, sadto I indulge myself to sports, subong sang covid wala na, wala na sports eh. Kay pagkatapos sang covid 19 restrictions was lightened so subong daw wala nagid kayo involvement.”-
Participant A

(Yes, let's say for example in sports. Way back, I indulge myself to sports but now that the virus came, I don't do that anymore. Even when the Covid-19 restrictions lightened, the interest of doing such activity is still so low and is not involved to sports anymore.) The participant's statement points out that he started losing interest in his hobbies when the community restrictions were implemented which made the sports activities to stop. Even programs that requires many audiences were prohibited which stopped the activities which could cater the talents and hobbies of many people and most of them only spend time with their phones, surfing and playing games.

“Kis-a sa hampang kis-a boring, mga ML kis-a sum-od man sagi hampang. Sumod maghampang bi nga ikaw lang permi isa, arang wala ka sabay hampang mas nami gid may ara upod. Tamad man mag lantaw Netflix.kung diin na bi may stable na nga internet ato na daw wala na gana kay daw sige2 na lang kay ara naman mo, diba lain sang una yah nga gapanginyawat pa sang signal adlaw-adlaw ma hampang gid na yah. Subong nga unay na internet makahampang lang pila ka game waay na himuyong na dayon.”-Participant E

(Sometimes I get bored playing mobile games and I get sick with it because I don't have someone with me to play with. I really prefer to play those games together with a partner or a friend. I get bored watching movies because I have so much time to do it and now, I don't feel like doing it more frequently anymore, I get sick of doing those activities every day.) Pandemic made us spend too much time just inside our homes for us to avoid being infected with the virus, and the participants lost their interest with their activities that they do almost every day, especially without any acquaintances to be with them.

If you have too many hobbies, then it would be inevitable you would become bored with one of them at some point as there would be other things competing for your attention. This pandemic did not only lead the participants to loss of interest in hobbies but also a loss of interest in their job as teacher. Participants tend to get tired with monitoring and giving children activities where they could cope up facing the Modular Distance Learning modality.

“Oo, sa ubra for example kung pandemic ang klase, mga students wala gakuha modules tapos daw ka kapoy sige follow up, daw ma dula-an ka na mag hatag sang grado.” **Participant H**

(I sometimes, lose interest in work during this pandemic because most of the students do not go to school to collect their modules and I get tired giving follow-ups to them and I'm having trouble grading students' performance.) Learners became tardy as the Modular Distance Learning go on, in terms of collecting and answering their modules and that gave the teacher a hard time rating students' performance because participants can't measure students' performance with modules with given answers at the back part. The learning and students' responses became more inaccurate, and learning is not at its best quality.

Thus, participants tend to lose their interest in the usual things they do, before the outbreak. It seems, as if there is a subconscious resistance to do things that require that you to leave your comfort zone. Something might fire your enthusiasm, but you lose it, when you see how much work or changes you need to make (Hall et al., 2020).

There are many reasons why people have trouble sleeping. Stress and anxiety often lead to insomnia and sleep problems. By the same token, lack of proper rest can contribute to stress. And because stress and sleep problems share such a reciprocal relationship, addressing one of these issues can often lead to improvements for the other (Wang et al., 2021). Stress are one of the major causes why a person has trouble sleeping. The participants stated that this time of pandemic, they have been through a lot of stress and activities that makes them feel tired.

One of the most mentioned reasons for trouble sleeping by the participants is the printing of modules and their personal experiences in this time of pandemic. In modular distance learning, there are many teachers experiencing stress in printing of modules and what are the effects of the modality to students' learning.

“Ou sir, may ara gid sang pag start sang MDL, yes kay wala ka kabalo kung ano imo nga eh expect sa matabo nga modality, kag kung ano ang mangin outcome sang discussion kag kung paano makatuon ang bata kag kung ano nga mga strategy nga pwede mo magamit. Mas dira ko na bother kay syempre as what I've said kagina PE teachers, may ara ta PE subject daw medyo mas gakabalisa ko kung pano ko ma deliver gid well ang akon nga lessons sa akon nga mga bata. Especially kay grade 10 ko daan mo so sa grade 10 daan more on cheerdancing ano pagid, so ma budlayan ko kung pano ko himoon gid kapin pa mostly sa ila wala gadgets.” **-Participant D**

(Since the MDL started, I could not sleep so well because I did not know what to expect in this type of modality and what is its outcome on how students will learn. I am also troubled on what strategies will I use to help student learn from my class effectively.

As what I have stated, we are MAPEH teachers and we teach Physical Education, wherein I am having trouble sleeping thinking on how I will deliver my lesson well. Especially, I am handling Grade 10 classes and the activities is more on cheer dancing and I am wondering if how I will make them perform the activity because most of my students don't have gadgets and internet.) MAPEH teachers print much greater number of sets of modules per week than any other subjects, which causes too much hassle on their part because MAPEH teachers will spend more time preparing the modules. This situation causes anxiety and stress to the participants which made her slumber difficult worrying about how to prepare that many modules in a short period of time using just inkjet printers.

One of the problems of teachers today is the resources of the students, where they could not disseminate instructions and interventions easily because most of their students do not have access in the internet, and no gadgets. Other reasons of participants why they ca not sleep well at night is the experience with their personal life, having trouble with their friends, co-teachers and businesses which was caused trouble by the Covid-19 pandemic. All over the world, millions of students are affected and some already gave up their status of being a student. And one of the biggest challenges to address the problem regarding learning is the availability of technological gadgets and internet connectivity. There were pieces of literature that supported the argument of this study and saw the needs and challenges of internet connections among students (Aboagye et al., 2021).

Thus, participants found that getting enough rest and sleep during this time of pandemic is challenging. According to recent research from the American Psychological Association, feeling stressed may cause you to go to great lengths to satisfy a craving for a drink or some sweets, but you're not likely to enjoy the indulgence any more than someone who is not stressed and consumes the same treat just for pleasure (Wang et al., 2021).

1.6. Relationship with Family and Loved Ones

As humans, we all need social connection. In fact, we can each thrive off of the stimulation of solving problems and everyday situations. When it comes to feelings of connection, there can be multiple ways of connecting with your loved ones (Rosa, 2019). Communicating with loved ones has a great impact on one's mental and emotional health. The participants stated that during this time of pandemic where restrictions of going outside are limited meeting with their loved ones is a bit challenging. Families, generally, are affected by the disruptions of the pandemic. However, these pressures disproportionately affect families who experience health and social inequities, including fewer financial and social resources, crowded homes and limited technology and Internet access (Laing, 2018).

Participants also follow health protocols during the pandemic and with this they can't meet or talk to their friends and loved ones anytime they want to. The only way for the participants to communicate with their loved ones is through social media, where they can chat, call and video call to keep in touch with one another.

“Always sir sa social media, amo gid na ang pinaka number 1 ko nga way para ma relieve ko akon self.”-Participant D

(I always communicate with my friends through social media, and that is my topmost way of giving myself relief.) The participant stated that, through communicating with friends in social media, gives her an ease from stress.

Most of the participants friends are from other cities and they have trouble bonding with them due to distance, but they still try to reach out with their friends, if they don't have a busy schedule. Participants tend to bond with their colleagues, and students if they want company, if their friends are unable to be with them.

“Usually akon mga circle of friends malang gid ara malang mga upod ko sa ubra. tapos laban ko nga friends di sa sagay, mga estudyante ko bi ligad, galagaw malang sila sa akon kay taga cadiz man gid ko, te ang mga barkada ko sa cadiz indi ko naman mayo makadto-an, pero may ari man ko di mga friends sa sagay.”-Participant E

(Usually, my circle of friends are just my co-teachers, and mostly my friends here in our city are my previous students and they just visit me here if they want to. Most of my friends are from the other city but I have friends here in this city.) The participant stated that he bonds with people near him to unwind if his friends are not around. Keeping in touch with friends is one of the priorities of the participants to avoid losing an acquaintance and communicating with them through social media were one of the reason why their friendship became stronger stated by the participant.

“Maybe at first kay sadto indi paman gid ta ka guwa mo sang first few months ano lang daw chat, mostly daw dira nagid nagbakod ang friendship namon sa through social media kay grabe pa ang kamustahanay kung na anon a kung ok pa ba sila. Kung ga ano sila sa ila balay nga wala guwa guwa. And then sang sini na nga pwede na maka gwa, so ga we meet up man japon. Kung kis-a gani every week daw ka amo gid na ang pinaka makakit-anay. Kis-a every other week. Sa isa ka bulan daw indi mahimo nga indi kami maka meet up.”-Participant B

(Maybe at first, during the first few months of the outbreak, we could not really go out and our only communication was through chat and I think that was where our friendship became stronger communicating in this situation asking if they were doing fine. Then, when the restrictions were lightened, we found time to meet with each other every week, or even just once for a month.) Meeting with friends or with family is challenging during this time of pandemic, because people should follow the protocol during the outbreak.

Finding time to be with them when the restrictions were lifted was the only choice of the participants. Thus, personal connections and finding company to participants is a trouble to participants. Hawkley points to evidence linking perceived social isolation with adverse health consequences including depression, poor sleep quality, impaired executive function, accelerated cognitive decline, poor cardiovascular function and impaired immunity at every stage of life (Novotney, 2019).

Though technologies and gadgets are great help for peoples' everyday lives, but there are some negative effects. While some forms of technology may have made positive changes in the world, there is evidence for the negative effects of technology and its overuse, as well. Social media and mobile devices may lead to psychological and physical issues, such as eyestrain and difficulty focusing on important tasks. They may also contribute to more serious health conditions, such as depression (Ma et al., 2021). Engaging in social media is a very addictive to some people, where they spend too much time to it. Relationships also can be affected by this, and the participants experience this problem.

“Magpuli ko sa balay, mga 6pm until matulog na. Pero daw indi man gid siling nga ga updanay gid permi kay si mama may ara man ubra, akon manghod ara man lang na sa iya kwarto ga hampang or lantaw Netflix, So ang bonding daw indi gid mayo guro maka bonding. Storyahanay lang, kung may eh share dira lang maka share, tapos indi gid lawig gid nga storyahanay.” -Participant A

(As I come home, we spend too little time bonding with each other, only from 6pm until we go to bed, but we don't get together all the time, because my mother have work to do. My brother spends his time more playing online games or watch movies so we really have too little time to talk with each other, unless there is something that one of us wants to share to the family.) Other than technologies, business are one of the factors also why participants tend to spend less time with their families. The participants stated that they spend more time alone in their homes than to spend time together with their family.

At some part, technologies are great idea for bonding also, to go with the interest of the rest of the family and a way to communicate also with your loved ones.

“Siguro, mga online games amon bonding kag istoryahanay. Para lang maka bond sila syempre ma sabay-sabay kaman sa ila hampang.” -Participant B

(I think playing and talking about online games are one of the activities we do to bond with each other. For me to be able to bond with them, so I have to do some of their interests also.) Even though technologies can ruin some of the relationships, it can also sometimes be one of the reasons to strengthen bonds. Participants stated also that through technologies or social media, they are able to communicate with their loved ones online when they are far from each other.

“Family sir, honestly daw almost 3 months nako wala ka puli sa amon. Pero may communication man kami gihapon sir sa social media sir, messenger call. Pero in person sir, amo na wala pako kapuli sa amon. Ang isa sang nag start ang pandemic daw 2 months nga wala kapuli kag ang isa bale mga 3 times na sir nga lawig ko indi makapuli kag makaupod sa ila personal.” -Participant D

(Honestly, as of now it is almost 3 months now that I am not able to go home, we just communicate using social media and calls. Last time, as the pandemic started I have been away from home for almost 2 months and this is the third time that I spend too much time away from them.) The participant stated that because his work stations is 4 hours

away from their home, he does not often go home to avoid getting infected with the virus and to lessen the expenses in traveling.

Thus, the participants spend too little time with their family with this problem. A family lacking healthy communication is like a ship without a rudder. It will flounder even in calm waters and will become dangerously out of control in a storm. (Carrión-Martínez et al., 2021). The COVID-19 crisis will not affect all families equally but may cause harm to children of low-income and less-educated parents, who tend to have lower academic and socioemotional skills compared to higher-income or more-educated parents already (Gayatri and Irawaty, 2022)

1.7. Workplace Performance

Over the course of your life, you set goals, big and small, that “force” you to give the best of yourself. That is not always the easiest thing to do. It requires time, it means putting some things on the back burner, and it often implies suffering. Sometimes you even have to filter what happens around you so that you do not get distracted (Carrión-Martínez et al., 2021). The participants experience this type of feeling which they think that their work and efforts are not enough to carry out their tasks and obligations.

“Daw ka kulangan ko kay ma compare ko akon self sa iban. Sila yah daw ok lang ila achievements tea ko yah kay bag-o lang ko te sa akon lang daw ka kulang gid sa akon pa experiences nga amo na nga maka survive sa isa ka gina himo, amo lang na. daw nakulangan lang ko, kay daw indi pako ready sa iban nga ulubrahon.”
-Participant H

(I myself am not satisfied with my efforts and I keep on comparing myself to others because I can see them attaining achievements, while I think that what I do is not enough because I am a newly hired teacher and lacks experiences. I think I’m not ready enough to completely done task correctly.) The participant tends to compare himself to others and causes him to be anxious about his performance as a teacher. He is troubled doing task because of thinking that those efforts might go to waste and even not enough to others. There is a situation where teachers were thinking frequently that they were scared to take risks because their efforts might just go to waste.

“During sa pila ka students nga printingan mo module tapos Makita mo man lang nga daw wala man lang gihapon pulos ang module nga gina hatag mo. Daw maka wala gana. Sagi ta print module tapos indi man lang ubrahon sang bata, tapos lantawon man lang ang likod sang module kay may answer key man lang. daw ka sala sang set up bi nga may answer key sa likod no?” **-Participant E**

(During the conduct of modality, we exert effort to print modules for a large number of students, but then you will just witness that it is kind of worthless, because many students do not exert efforts to answer their modules and there are some students that only refers their answer on the key answer provided at the back of every module). Many of the teachers are bothered with the performance of the students with the Modular Distance Learning Modality with modules that has few information that is not enough for students to understand the lessons and has key answers at the back.

Even performance tasks at times, participants tend to observe that the students do not answer this kind of activities carefully and as a result, students get low scores. Teachers are distracted with that notion and mostly feels useless as one of the instruments for students learning. Thus, participants are having difficulties in valuing their efforts. Learning to value your own effort is the first step of personal growth. It means traveling along an uncertain path, stepping carefully to avoid pitching over the edge. Understanding this is crucial for a very simple reason: the path to achieving your goals can be terribly lonely (Gayatri and Irawaty, 2022).

The participants stated that conflicts within their workplace is present in their stations. Many full-time employees spend more of their waking hours with co-workers than they do with their spouses and families. As such, it is important to allow employees the opportunity to build quality relationships with their co-workers (Rosa, 2019). The participants stated that they experience workstation conflicts more often during the Modular Distance Learning. The reason for that is the delay of submission of modules from subject teachers to the advisers and some conflicts arise because of lost modules.

“During pandemic, oo damo. Example of that is, siguro sa ano gid sa retrieving and releasing sang modules. From subject teachers to advisers and vice versa. Kay sang pag kwan gid sang modular distance learning ang naga kwan sang modules ang naga release sang modules is the adviser and the one who prints the module is the subject teacher, pero later on nga ang mga papel sang mga bata madula ni adviser so indi ma retrieve ni subject teacher so it will reflect on the grades of the students because their paper is incomplete so later the parents will argue ngaa ang bata nila nugbo kag wala grado kay sometimes ang summative test will not be turned over by subject teachers to the adviser.” -Participant A

(During the pandemic we had a lot of conflicts, one example is that the releasing and retrieving of modules. From subject teachers to advisers and vice versa, because as the modality started advisers are the one who releases the modules and the subject teachers are the ones who prints the modules, but later on advisers tend to loses the papers of students and will not be retrieved and graded by the subject teacher and it reflects on students' performance and grades. Because of that, parents question the subject teachers about why their children get low or no grades because not only the modules are misplaced, sometimes including the summative tests also.) The participants stated that most of the situations they encounter in their school where conflict starts.

The participants tend to get disappointed with their co-teachers because of this circumstances where quarrel starts. The most common conflicts based to the participants are misunderstanding each other's character and attitude towards another.

“May ara gid. Mostly sa mga misunderstanding. Siguro indi man sya nag away gid, daw may ara lang workmate nga daw indi gid ko nami-an sa ila. Mga indi bestfriend sa school. May indi lang ko gusto sa ila nga mga practices, sa ila behavior kag attitude sa school.” -Participant B

(There are some instances, which misunderstanding occurs. I have some workmates that I do not get along so well because I do not like them that much, but we do not go too far. I just do not like their practices, behavior and attitude in our school.) There are responses from the participants also, that they are having conflicts and misunderstanding with their school heads because they doesn't like the way they are being handled as subordinates.

“May ara kami. Sa school head namon, gin petisyonan namon in terms of corruption, amo na amon gin reklamo sa iya, gin patawag kami sa deped isa-isa kag gin pa explain.” -Participant E

(Actually we have, about our school head. We signed a petition about her regarding the corruption that was happening in our school, and we were called by the Division Office to explain how did this happen.) The participant stated that their school head sold some of their resources without them knowing and without receipt and deed of sale.

Thus, the participants find workmate relationships are difficult to maintain. Conflicts can be present in any workplace. If left unaddressed, they can affect employee morale and hinder performance (Jones and Kessler, 2020). Thus, migrating from traditional or blended learning to a fully virtual and online delivery strategy will not happen overnight and thus has been associated with many challenges (Jones and Kessler, 2020).

1.8. Innovations made by Teachers

W.H.O. defines physical activity as any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure. Physical activity refers to all movement including during leisure time, for transport to get to and from places, or as part of a person's work. Both moderate- and vigorous-intensity physical activity improve health. Outdoor physical activity holds strong potential as an effective coping and preventive strategy given its many well-documented physical, social, and mental health benefits for people of all ages, especially those with or at risk of developing chronic diseases (Ma et al., 2021)

“Amo to, exercise ga skip rope, lifting weights kung may time kung weekend amo lang na akon gina himo sa physical health ko.” -Participant H

(I exercise using skipping rope and lifting weights if I have time on weekends, and that's all I do for my physical health.) The participants after experiencing challenge during the pandemic, having a hard time keeping themselves do physical activities, but they found some ways. Rather than jogging outdoors, at the streets or at the park, the participant bought skipping rope for him to jog and dumbbells so that he can still work out inside their house, while they are safe from getting infected with the virus.

Eating healthy foods was one of the ways the participant do to keep themselves fit even if they do few exercises. There are many ways to keep your body healthy other than exercise. Eating habits can also be a great contribution to one's health. According to (Aperribai et al., 2020) what you eat is closely linked to your health. Balanced nutrition

has many benefits. By making healthier food choices, you can prevent or treat some conditions. These include heart disease, stroke, and diabetes. A healthy diet can help you lose weight and lower your cholesterol, as well.

“I keep myself fit about what I eat. Not so much activity but I am picky when it comes to eating.” -Participant A

The participant stated that though he exercises rarely, he keeps himself healthy by eating nutritious foods and avoiding unhealthy lifestyle. Food is key to personal health, as well as to the health of the planet given that current patterns of food production and consumption have considerable environmental impacts (Hagger et al., 2020). He avoids consuming too much alcohol and does not smoke. During this time of pandemic, though participants are too busy and had unhealthy routines because of additional workloads, participants still find some ways to keep themselves healthy to avoid being sick and weak.

“Ga try ko kis-a work out nga, ang mga bagay nga simple gina himo ko complicated. Kis-a ang halakwaton gina dugangan ko kis-a ginabilin ko danay ang iban para masaka panaog ko exercise.” -Participant E

(Sometimes, I try working out by doing things complicated instead of making it simple. Sometime when I have to carry something, I carry things as many as I can to increase the weight and sometimes, I do not carry all the things that I have to carry for me to walk up and down the stairs many times.) The respondent stated that for him do be fit doing his job and at the same time doing exercise, he makes simple things complicated to exert more effort as a form of exercise. The sudden changes in people’s lifestyle include, but are not limited to, physical activities and exercise. Kaur et al (2020) have reported that COVID-19 home confinement has resulted in a decrease in all levels of physical activities and about 28% increase in daily sitting time as well as increase in unhealthy pattern of food consumption. Similar results are also reported by other researchers (Hagger et al., 2020). Thus, the participants during the Modular Distance Learning, find ways to exercise on their own, without going out and going to gyms in places where there’s too many people, which for them is effective enough to keep themselves physically healthy. Exercise is an important part of a healthy lifestyle. Exercise prevents health problems, builds strength, boosts energy, and can help you reduce stress. It can also help you maintain a healthy body weight and curb your appetite (Orte et al., 2020).

According to Abdel-Fattah (2020), emotional health is the ability to cope with and manage emotions. It was also the ability to have positive relationships. Mental health is the ability to think clearly and make good decisions. It was also the ability to cope with stress and manage emotions. The participants experience many things which challenge their emotional and mental health capacity and how they can cope up with it. To cope with these challenges, the participants seek company from their friends, families and loved ones to share their problems and things that troubles them so much.

“Ga share ko mga problems amo na kung may gina overthink, ga chat ko sakon mga friends kay lagyo sila, sila akon ginpangayo-an bulig kag gina pangayo-an advice or sa akon family.” -Participant E

(I share my problems with my friends through chat because they were far away from me. They are the ones whom I seek help and ask for advice and also my family.) We all have to face problems in our life journey. Some people do not share their problems with others because they think others cannot solve their problems. They do not want family members to become stressed. Sharing problems with family is very important for happiness because that helps to free up your mind (Carrion-Martinez et al., 2021). Venting ourselves out to our loved ones is one of the most effective way of clearing our mind from the things that bothers us most. It was a great way to avoid anxiety and depression because according to the participants talking to someone about your problems is helpful to avoid being stressful.

“Gakape ko, ga make sure ko nga kung daw ma stress ko sakon nga ulubrahon makadto ko sa kapehan. Amo na bisan ako lang isa ma pa aircon kag mangape, tapos ma sound trip tapos amo na, daw ginatagaan ko reward akon self nga makaon, nga indi ko tipiron akon kaugalingon kay gin pangabudlayan ko man ni.” -Participant E

(I drink coffee alone, I make sure that if I feel stressed I go to a coffee shop. I drink coffee or eat alone and listening to music as a reward for myself and I'm telling myself that I don't have to be stingy about those things because I've worked hard to earn money for it.) While others seek presence of peers in order for them to unwind and let their stress out, there are some people who wants to be alone in solitude to free themselves from stress.

Although, it is equally necessary to socialize and meet new people in today's day and age, taking some time off for ourselves every day can prove to be extremely beneficial as it gives us time to collect our thoughts and ideas, helps us discover new dimensions of our personality and also teaches us to value the importance of our own company (De Vos, 2022). This statement tells that although we need other people, and socialize being alone and enjoying our own company can be of great help also to lessen the stress and to know ourselves better and to learn how to value ourselves. The participants stated that they often spend time alone to de-stress themselves through watching movies and doing their hobbies and playing games which, they enjoy to get away from their world as teachers. Emotional and mental health is important because it's a vital part of your life and impacts your thoughts, behaviors and emotions. Being healthy emotionally can promote productivity and effectiveness in activities like work, school or caregiving (Abdel-Fattah, 2020).

Social Health is a term that refers to the ways in which people create healthy and positive interpersonal relationships with one another. Having good social health helps people improve their emotional wellbeing and feel supported in their daily lives. Our social health and wellness is measured by the relationships and connections we have to others in the world around us (Aboagye et al., 2021). The participants experience stress and hardships

this time of pandemic and they need time to unwind and meet their friends or new other people to spend time with.

The participants stated that the most people they spend time with during this pandemic is their families if they are given a chance. They call their friends to bond with them like eating, playing or drinking, or conducting fellowships together to relieve some stress.

“Gajoin mn ko mga fellowships for young professionals para mka-connect with them.”-Participant G

(I join fellowships for young professionals to connect with them.) Being socially aware and respectful is one of the things that will help you become socially healthy and avoid conflicts from other persons.)

“Always engage sa akon nga mga peers, sa akon nga mga co teachers, sa akon mga friends amo na ginahimo ko and if may mga problems nga mag arise syempre try to respect each other’s opinions.”-Participant H

(I always engage myself with peers, with my co-teachers, and my friends and if there are problems that arise, we try to respect each other’s opinions.) The participants reiterated that, to avoid conflicts and problems between other people, one should be an open-minded person that no one is alike and always have individual differences, and so respect to one another is the core to harmonious relationship in the society.

According to the Australian Government, “social relationships are protective of mental health”. The quantity and quality of our relationships significantly impact our mental and physical well-being. Being able to build and maintain good levels of social wellness enables us to develop valuable interpersonal relationships with others. These relationships comprise of intimate, family, platonic, professional and friendships. (Aboagye et al., 2021).

Conclusions

This study aimed to determine the challenges and innovations of MAPEH teachers amidst Covid-19 pandemic. Thus, the following were the findings of the said study. As the Covid19 pandemic spread all over the country, conducting classes and carrying out duty while maintaining their holistic health became a great challenge to teachers in terms of physical, emotional, mental and social aspects and how MAPEH teachers innovate to address the said challenges.

In terms of physical health where the participants were having difficulty in getting enough rest and doing exercise outside their homes and in gyms to keep themselves physically healthy, due to the danger of acquiring the said virus when in contact to public places and random people. On the other hand, participants thought of the possible exercises that they can perform while just inside their homes or workplaces to keep themselves healthy.

Eating a proper diet to ensure that their bodies ingest the desired nutrients to keep themselves and immune system healthy. Emotionally and mentally, the participants tend to experience stress with the effects of sudden changes, fear and worrying about their work, lives, their students and their family caused by the said pandemic. When participants felt distress, they utilize the presence of the person nearest to them to share their thoughts and feelings to express and to free themselves from the burden they felt. They vented out to someone they know they can trust and understand their situations and also spending time in solitude to get to know and understand themselves more and as well as giving themselves a peace of mind. Socially, adjusting with the current situations where going out and meeting new people and roam around places are challenging.

Furthermore, responsibilities of the teachers during this pandemic is a tough and stressful challenge to teachers, wherein they most likely to experience workplace conflicts due to misunderstanding and negligence of duty, in which participants took actions in order to understand each other and settle conflicts to have a harmonious interpersonal relationship within their workplace to perform efficiently as teaching workforce of their respective stations.

Recommendations

After identifying the challenges and innovations of MAPEH teachers amidst pandemic in terms of maintain holistic health through their experiences, the researcher came up with the following recommendations that would benefit MAPEH and other subject teachers as well as the person concern.

It is highly recommended that school administrators should formulate programs which would lessen the risks of teachers to travel publicly with the risk of virus infection and create a systematic designation of workloads to avoid overworking and overtime. The teachers should only be the persons administering the learning and should be given time to help students and focus on being a teacher by giving the printing of module responsibilities to other possible qualified persons that should only focus on the said activity. The teachers should be given more emotional and mental health management programs or orientations to help them and their peers to aid correlating with the needs of their peer and also promote social relationship developments to avoid conflicts and have a progressive performance as school faculties.

The future researchers should conduct a study focusing only on either of the said aspects to dig deeper about each challenges and innovations the teachers experience which would emphasize the aid the challenges more specifically.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The data gathered are kept with outmost confidentiality and an issuance of informed consent was observed. Because of the sensitivity of the data and information to be obtained, the interview was conducted to the participants personally. The transcriptions were destroyed after the final defense. The researcher did not compel the participants to answer the questionnaire if they find it uncomfortable. The school head was notified regarding the conduct of this study and its possible effect to the class schedule and students' performance. The participants were informed of the study's objectives and that their honest statements and answers were handled with strict secrecy and were solely used for research purposes. Whatever their responses are will not affect their performance as teachers of their respective stations.

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